

Recent Research in Network Security

Network security and Data analytics is an important to present society where information technology and services pass through each facet of our lives. However, it is demanding to achieve, as technology is changing at rapid speed and our systems turn into ever more complex. We are gradually more dependent upon such information and communications infrastructures, and the threats we face are organized and exploit our dependency by the attackers or cyber criminals. Moreover, cyber space is considered as fifth battlefield after land, air, water and space. The focal objective of the Special Issue on “Recent research in network security” is to provide insight mechanisms while handling data; provide conceptual understanding of network security issues, challenges and mechanisms; develop basic skills of secure network architecture and explain the theory behind the security of networks, analytics and different cryptographic algorithms. It is to present the most recent challenges and developments in data analytics and networks. It also provides a forum for researchers, practitioners and educators to present and discuss the most recent innovations, trends, and concerns, practical challenges encountered and the solutions adopted in these fields.

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